

1 **Computational vs. qualitative: Analyzing different approaches in identifying networked**
2 **frames during the Covid-19 crisis**

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28 With the exponential growth of big data, automated methods have been used in the social
29 sciences to analyze large text data, e.g., tweet corpora. In particular, natural language processing
30 (NLP) offers researchers the ability to examine frames in the textual content. Researchers have
31 explored the extent to which computational techniques can be used to discover media frames, but

32 more research is needed if we are to understand the strengths and weaknesses of automated
33 techniques for identifying frames in different contexts and languages. Indeed, the existing
34 literature in this area has focused on mainstream languages such as English (Baden et al., 2022).
35 As a result, we know less about other less-studied languages, such as Persian. To address these
36 gaps, we have done a comparative analysis of the Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA) topic model
37 with human-driven coding to identify networked frames on Iranian Twitter.
38 This paper is organized as follows. First, we provide an overview of the promises and
39 weaknesses of automated approaches to frame extraction and point out the existing gaps in this
40 area. Then, we explain our approach to developing a comparative study to address these gaps. In
41 the Methods section, we describe the processes of data collection, human-driven coding, and
42 LDA implementation. Our empirical analyses focus on a large corpus of 4,165,177 Persian
43 tweets collected during the early months of the coronavirus crisis in Iran. Nicholls & Culpepper
44 (2020) argue that our most important question is not the ability of computational methods to
45 extract frames but rather what type of input data they are likely to succeed with. Therefore, we
46 input three different samples of the same dataset to understand which ones LDA performs best
47 on. The smallest of these samples were subject to intensive qualitative coding practice. This
48 process was used to measure the performance of LDA in detecting frames and to validate the
49 LDA result. After presenting the results, we discuss the contribution of this study to ongoing
50 research on comparing computational techniques with traditional qualitative methods.

51 **A Computational Approach to Identifying Networked Frames**

52 Frames are discursive packages people impose on their lived experiences to make sense of them
53 (Chong & Druckman, 2007; Gamson & Modigliani, 1989). Despite the ongoing conceptual dispute
54 among communication scholars (De Vreese, 2005; Lecheler & De Vreese, 2019), we follow
55 Entman (1993, p. 52) in understanding framing as "[selecting] some aspects of a perceived reality
56 and make them more salient in a communicating text." Framing analysis is an important research
57 strand in political science and communication studies (Lev-On, 2018). Framing analysis could
58 enhance our knowledge of the extent to which and how media, politicians, etc., try to manipulate
59 reality and from what point of view (Entman, 2003).

60 Social researchers have traditionally used qualitative methods such as thematic and content
61 analysis in frame detection. However, with the advent of large text datasets, automated techniques,
62 e.g., natural language processing (NLP), outperform traditional text analyses through their ability
63 to analyze large text data with minimal time and effort (Barberá et al., 2021). Moreover, automatic
64 methods are applicable to a wider variety of settings and can be used without extensive adaptation
65 (Scharkow, 2013). On the other hand, the existing literature suggests that there is some
66 exaggeration regarding the fact that machine learning approaches, e.g., topic modeling techniques,
67 are inherently superior to the current manual process in terms of time and cost savings (Hilbert et
68 al., 2019). Aside from several challenging machine-derived measurements (see De Grove et al.,
69 2020; Grimmer & Stewart, 2013; Hilbert et al., 2019), machines have little understanding of
70 human language, which brings the strengths of qualitative human-driven coding to the fore (Boyd
71 & Crawford, 2012; Scharkow, 2013). Moreover, some studies show that a large dataset's carefully
72 and deliberately coded sample can give similar results to what machines produce (De Grove et
73 al., 2020).

74 Nevertheless, in recent years, automated methods (from supervised to unsupervised techniques)
75 have gained importance in frame analysis. The use of supervised methods in framing analysis
76 carries significant risk (Nicholls & Culpepper, 2020). Such methods rely on predefined frames,
77 i.e., closed codebooks or pre-constructed scenarios, which tend to project the researchers' prior
78 background, knowledge, and assumptions onto the dataset (Walter & Ophir, 2019). In this way,
79 those frames that were not anticipated by the theory could be neglected, which is known as the
80 "drunk under the streetlight" syndrome (Nicholls & Culpepper, 2020).

81 Unsupervised methods are also used to identify grounded frames in text corpora. While some
82 techniques, such as the k-means clustering algorithm and evolutionary factor analysis (EFA), are
83 commonly used, topic modeling is much more accessible and reliable (Maier et al., 2018, Lind et
84 al., 2021). There are several versions of topic models, especially in computer science, such as the
85 Correlated Topic Model (CTM) (Blei & Lafferty, 2007). Nevertheless, two models remain the
86 most important members of the topic modeling family to date: The structural Topic Model (STM)
87 and Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA). The use of STM is somewhat idiosyncratic to political
88 science and computational communication work. However, the two techniques are largely
89 identical in their approach, e.g., both use the bag-of-words assumption, where the order of words

90 in each document is ignored (Nicholls & Culpepper, 2020). Nevertheless, for the purposes of this
91 study, we choose LDA.

92 LDA is an unsupervised probabilistic model that analyzes a set of documents and predicts the
93 themes that make up the collection (Blei, 2012; Blei et al., 2003). LDA is increasingly used in
94 communication studies because of its ability to quickly and efficiently explore the thematic
95 structures of a large set of text documents (Maier et al., 2018). A major advantage is that, in
96 contrast to supervised methods, topics are inferred from a given collection without prior
97 knowledge, thus avoiding the so-called streetlight syndrome (Maier et al., 2018). Another
98 advantage of LDA is its mixed membership approach (Grimmer & Stewart, 2013, p. 18). Mixed
99 membership means that each document can consist of more than one topic. This is a useful
100 assumption when analyzing networked frames.

101 Some communication researchers are skeptical about the capabilities of LDA for frame detection,
102 arguing that the output of the probabilistic algorithm is a topic, not a frame, as understood in
103 communication research (Nicholls & Culpepper, 2020). A frame is a linguistic phenomenon that
104 consequently carries a high degree of human meaning (Van Gorp, 2007). On the other hand, a
105 topic is a computational construct representing a probability distribution over words in terms of
106 NLP (Blei et al., 2003, p. 996). In particular, Walter & Ophir (2019) find the equation of topics
107 with frames problematic. In their view, a topic can be a frame element but not necessarily an entire
108 frame package. On the other hand, several studies argue that this computational construct is
109 relatively adjacent to a frame (DiMaggio et al., 2013). Jurafsky & Martin (2020) described LDA
110 as an extremely useful tool for discovering topical structures in documents. In other words, LDA
111 explores the "hidden" thematic structure of a given collection of texts (Maier et al., 2018, p. 93).
112 In this sense, scholars have insisted on considering the themes revealed by these models as an
113 operationalization of policy frames (DiMaggio et al., 2013; Gilardi et al., 2021). From another
114 perspective, researchers suggest that using the results of LDA under certain conditions could be
115 helpful in frame detection. Ylä-Anttila et al. (2022) argue that 'topics' of topic models can be used
116 as a useful proxy for frames if (1) frames are operationalized as connections between concepts; (2)
117 theme-specific data are used; and (3) topics are validated in terms of frame analysis.

118 Although existing research has mainly focused on different types of media frames (e.g., generic
119 and topic-specific frames), little is known about the effectiveness of computational techniques in
120 identifying a new type of framing that has emerged with the advent of social media. Networked
121 framing is not cascading, vertical, restrictive, or organization-centered like mass media frames.
122 Meraz and Papacharissi (2013) understand networked framing as a process whereby actors
123 circulate information and add their own layers of information, knowledge, beliefs, and experiences
124 on the fly. In contrast to the static and permanent nature of frames in mass media, networked
125 frames, e.g., Twitter frames, are constantly revised, re-articulated, and re-circulated by both the
126 masses and the elite (Meraz & Papacharissi, 2013). The particular nature of networked frames
127 makes them even more difficult to identify using automated methods. To date, there is no further
128 research evaluating the potential and weaknesses of computational techniques in identifying
129 networked frames. Most researchers have focused on mainstream languages. Therefore, we do not
130 know how automated techniques work for other, less studied languages such as Persian. This paper
131 addresses these gaps by conducting a comparative analysis using LDA and human-driven
132 qualitative coding in extracting networked frames in the Iranian Twittersphere.

133 **Methods**

134 *Data and Samples*

135 We collected the data in the early months of the coronavirus crisis in Iran from Twitter REST-
136 API. The emergence of Covid-19 on December 31, 2019, in China threw the entire world into
137 complete shock. Almost immediately, many countries started to impose quarantine and stringent
138 restrictions to stop the spread of Covid-19. Due to these prohibitions, many people did not go
139 outside. Instead, they discussed this unfamiliar fact on social media. Social media data, in
140 particular tweets, are especially well suited to studying how people frame crises of this nature in a
141 networked space. No wonder social media are considered sites of rich "cultural meaning-making"
142 (Murthy, 2016). When the Covid-19 pandemic struck, social media particularly took a prominent
143 role, as people turned to these platforms to form collective consciousnesses, share stories and
144 messages of hope, and discuss new events or natural disasters as they happened.

145 Iran was one of the countries that was seriously affected by this crisis. At the time of writing this
146 paper, August 2022, the number of people who have died and gone infected hovers around 8

147 million, according to official figures. The first cases were reported on February 19, 2020. The
148 research team had begun collecting data a month earlier because of suspicions that the virus had
149 spread across the country earlier than the government would admit. This allowed us to study the
150 framework even before the country was involved. Data collection began on January 21, 2020. We
151 continued this process until April 29, 2020, for almost 4 months. We collected all tweets that
152 contained corresponding hashtags (#Corona in Persian, with all its variations). Then, we filtered
153 the data in Persian since the spelling of Corona is identical in Persian and Arabic. As a result,
154 4,165,177 tweets were collected.

155 In the next step, we created three different samples using social network analysis. These samples
156 were part of our approach to validate and evaluate the results of this research. First, we created a
157 retweet (RT) network¹ as the first sample (n= 2,519,915 tweets). Then, we used PageRank
158 centrality (Easley & Kleinberg, 2010) to identify the 50 most influential users in the RT network.
159 We formed the second sample and extracted all tweets sent by these users in the RT network (n=
160 7,658 tweets). Finally, we selected a random representative subset of sample 2. Based on the
161 Cochran formula for calculating the sample size of a finite population, we selected 5,056 tweets
162 (confidence level= 99%.) as sample 3. All samples were used in the computation phase, but the
163 qualitative analysis was completed only with the last sample. While our selection of the 50 top
164 users might be questionable in a discursive sense, that is beside the point in terms of the purposes
165 of this study.

166 *Human-driven Coding Process*

167 To avoid the streetlight syndrome, we followed Van Gorp's (2010) two-stage mixed inductive-
168 deductive approach to qualitative frame identification. In the first stage, we coded our content
169 inductively, using open coding to elicit potential frames. This was followed by a deductive phase
170 where we used the elements of these frame packages to code frame prevalence in a controlled and
171 reproducible manner (Nicholls & Culpepper, 2020, p. 4). We added one more step to the first phase
172 to scrutinize the process of qualitative interpretation. Subsequently, the samples were coded in
173 three steps, namely in two inductive steps and one deductive step.

¹ The retweet network (RT) is a directed graph G. The nodes are Twitter users and the edges are retweet links between users. An edge is directed from user A, who posts a tweet, to user B, who retweets it.

174 The inductive steps followed Saldana's two-step approach (2015). In the first step, coders (n=3)
175 inductively developed a codesheet by closely reading the tweets. This codesheet was broad—and
176 it included many open codes. After completing the open coding and team discussions, the team
177 would identify sets of codes and create a preliminary codebook. By grouping the open codes into
178 general themes, 71 themes were identified. This codebook was used as the baseline for the second
179 round. In this round, the coders coded the entire sample based on precedent coding (Saldaña, 2015,
180 p. 209). The goal of this step was to discover the core themes in the tweet sample. The result was
181 a final codesheet with 16 networked frames. The 16 identified main frames and their 71 sub-frames
182 (frames identified in the first step) are listed in Appendix 1. The main networked frames are also
183 discussed in the Findings section.

184 We used the final codesheet in the deductive step to quantify the codes across all sample tweets.
185 The result of this deductive step was used to identify the dominant themes in the sample. Of course,
186 we did not rely only on these numbers. We also used the qualitative notes and memos from the
187 previous rounds to gain a deeper understanding of the grounded frames. In addition, each tweet
188 could be coded for multiple frames. Our decision was consistent with LDA mixed-membership.
189 In addition, quantifying the qualitative codes creates a more consistent basis for comparing LDA
190 topics with qualitative frames.

191 *Topic Modeling*

192 We followed the comprehensive approach of Maier et al. (2018) to implement topic modeling in
193 this study. They provide several steps for using LDA in communication research: appropriate pre-
194 processing, selection of appropriate parameters, and evaluation and validation of LDA output.

195 First, we removed stop words, punctuation marks, numbers, emojis, smileys, and other special
196 characters. As the Persian language lacks lowercase and uppercase characters, capitalization or
197 lack thereof does not apply here. In addition, we did not perform stemming and lemmatization on
198 the research dataset, as previous research has demonstrated that these features do not significantly
199 improve the performance of topic models (Jurafsky & Martin, 2020; Schofield et al., 2017).
200 Moreover, to our knowledge, no reliable dictionary performs these features in Persian.

201 Furthermore, the choice of the K-value, i.e., the number of topics to be generated by the LDA
202 algorithm, is a critical decision that significantly affects the result. However, although several K-
203 value-estimation techniques have been implemented in Python libraries (Baden et al., 2020; Maier
204 et al., 2018; Rodriguez & Storer, 2020), there is not yet a standard method for calculating the K-
205 value.

206 This study used the *LdaModel* algorithm embedded in Python's *Gensim* library. Gensim (Generate
207 Similar) is a powerful Python library that processes plain texts and uses unsupervised machine
208 learning algorithms (Jelodar et al., 2019). Gensim uses topic coherence to estimate K. Topic
209 coherence measures the score of a single topic by measuring the degree of semantic similarity
210 between high-scoring words in the topic. We calculated topic coherence for all samples in this
211 study to determine the possible K-values. Our analyses yielded K=16, 12, 9, and 7 for the RT
212 network; K= 10, 7, and 3 for sample 2; and K= 18, 15, 12, and 8 for sample 3. In addition to these
213 automatically selected values, we decided to add values of 5 and 20 for all samples. Thus, our
214 efforts to select the best Ks are not limited to automated statistical algorithms. We then manually
215 reviewed all tweets to see which K score worked best for each sample. Our evaluations revealed
216 that the consistency of the results varies for different K-values. For some values, we got more
217 scattered topics that are difficult to group. Nevertheless, after several rounds of checking the data
218 for all possible Ks, we chose K=12 for RT networks, K=10 and K =12 for samples 2 and 3,
219 respectively. These values provide us with the most coherent sets of topics.

220 Topic model output in most cases includes a family of words in different categories that may
221 appear inconsistent and meaningless. In other words, the topics do not speak for themselves. They
222 must be interpreted by humans (Grimmer & Stewart, 2013). While some statistical approaches,
223 e.g., topic coherence as we used in this research, have been proposed to capture the reliability of
224 LDA (see Maier et al., 2018), we agree with Nicholls and Culpepper (2020), who argue that there
225 are no quantitative measures that can calculate the quality of LDA topics (p. 8). Moreover, various
226 obstacles, such as the lack of required dictionaries and software packages, make the available
227 metrics even more inapplicable to Persian texts.

228 As a result, The vast majority of the literature suggests that manual labeling based on close reading
229 of documents is a more reliable method for assessing LDA topics (e.g., Elgesem et al., 2015;

230 Koltsova & Koltcov, 2013; Maier et al., 2018; Rodriguez & Storer, 2020). Following Roberts et
231 al. (2014) and Gerring (2001), Nicholls and Culpepper (2020) propose three criteria for
232 understanding the quality of LDA topics: 1) the suitability of topics to our theoretical
233 understanding of a frame, 2) the internal coherence of each topic, and 3) the external differentiation
234 from other topics.

235 We sought to ensure these criteria through a multi-level approach. First, we crawled through the
236 top 10 words in each topic. This was followed by examining the top 200 tweets from each topic in
237 each sample to gain a more profound understanding of their content and coherence. Maier et al.
238 (2018) observed that this is a time-consuming but likely consistent and indispensable step in
239 validating LDA output. Finally, we attempted to assign representative and reliable labels to LDA
240 topics where possible.

241 **Findings**

242 *Qualitative Results*

243 Figure 1 shows the networked frames identified by human coders and the proportion of each in
244 sample 3. A total of 16 networked frames (with 71 sub-frames) were identified during the
245 qualitative human-driven coding process. See Appendix 1.1 for a complete list of main frames and
246 sub-frames.

247 **Fig. 1.**

248 Fig. 1 shows that "Finding the culprit (FC)," "Condemning repressive/deceptive/misusing actions
249 (RDM)," and "Infected people (IP)" were the most dominant frames in the study sample. The
250 details of these frames are provided in appendix 1.2. In brief, the dominant frames consisted of
251 critical narratives focused on the Iranian state's engagement with the crisis. Iranian users also
252 displayed personal sentiments, stories, and affective messages mixed with news and information.
253 To a lesser extent, Iranian users devoted their attention to the situation around the world, focusing
254 on China's role in getting the world into deep trouble. In addition to these frames, the research
255 team systematically examined all networked frames and their sub-frames. The result of this
256 systematic examination was used throughout the study to draw more solid conclusions when
257 comparing the qualitative results with the LDA results.

258 As we argued in the previous sections, qualitative coding of Persian tweets is not as straightforward
259 and direct as we originally thought. Several challenges were encountered during the manual
260 qualitative coding in this project.

261 First, vowels often play a crucial role in shaping the meaning of a Persian text. Unlike in English,
262 vowels are not usually written in Persian scripts. As a result, the tone and meaning of a word or a
263 sentence could be misconstrued by automatic word and sentence identification programs. For
264 example, a user tweeted a message which could be roughly translated as "The regime is very good
265 at controlling the virus!". In plain language, this sentence can be interpreted as a tweet in favor of
266 the regime. But here is the difference. The word "very" is written in Persian as خیلی. In this form,
267 this tweet is a serious message admiring the regime. But the user changed this word to خَعیلی. In
268 this form, the user put a short vowel (ـَ a) on the letter خ. The user also added the letter ع to
269 emphasize this change. In this way, the user changed the tone of the text from serious to sarcastic.
270 Unlike خیلی, the word خَعیلی is negatively charged. Therefore, this tweet should be coded as an anti-
271 regime message berating the regime for its bungling incompetence in dealing with the Covid-19
272 pandemic. A common theme of this tweet is that the regime's incompetence has negatively affected
273 the public health and well-being of people.

274 The above example shows the complexity of interpreting a Persian tweet. It illustrates how much
275 work it is to understand Persian text. Such challenges are not limited to the problems posed by
276 vowels. Sarcastic messages with embedded metaphors and ironies are common on Persian Twitter.
277 For example, one user tweeted, " Regarding the terrible spread of the coronavirus, God has
278 announced through Jannati that no one should come to my party." This message was sarcastic, and
279 one should know the meaning to interpret it correctly. First, "God's feast" refers to Ramadan, a
280 month devoted to fasting and prayer, during which Muslims were particularly vulnerable to the
281 spread of covid-19 as they would gather to pray together. Because of the Covid-19 crisis, this was
282 not possible at that time. Therefore, this user's most recent tweet posed a challenge to this religious
283 metaphor. But there is more. The user did not just write that God announced it but that God
284 announced it by Jannati. Ahmad Jannati is the chairman of the Guardian Council in Iran. He is 95
285 years old, and Iranians usually joke about him as immortal. In this tweet, the user wanted to imply
286 that Jannati and God are the same age, so God instructed him to announce the news. This example
287 shows how complicated and rich a short text can be in different discursive elements.

288 The above example also illustrates the problem of mixed frames. Tweets usually do not contain a
289 clear and distinct frame. Users mix different topics together and vary their tone (e.g., serious,
290 sarcastic, etc.). This makes it more difficult to identify the frames in each tweet. To illustrate, One
291 user tweeted, "The situation in Iran is critical! Do not expect anything from the regime! Please
292 follow the health instructions yourself! Imam Khomeini hospital in Saghez is completely
293 quarantined! 12 people suspected to be infected with #Covid -19 are in this hospital." In this tweet,
294 we find at least three frames: FC (IRI), IP (statistics), and Covid-19 adversity (following health
295 guidelines). Therefore, we believe that even human coders with a closed codebook are likely to
296 code the same text differently. It is not easy to decide which frame is dominant in this text. We
297 tried to reduce this problem by coding for multiple frames in this study. But the problem of
298 dominant frames still exists.

299 Finally, we find users changing words and phrases out of context in creative and sometimes
300 confusing ways. A tweet shows how the process works: "And my thorns fell! If the situation is so
301 critical, why did they not announce it?" When we hear this message, we should not think of our
302 own genital hair but of Iranian users' use of the slang term "My wool fell! " where "wool" literally
303 refers to genital hair. It is used to express a sense of shock, like "holy shit." The user has used
304 "thorn" as a metonym for "wool" to mitigate wool's scatological and prurient connotations. Such
305 a text would be impossible for a machine model to interpret in this way. Moreover, human coders
306 should have a sense of user colloquialisms and innovations to understand the message fully.

307 The above challenges not only make it difficult for machine algorithms to understand the meaning
308 behind a text but also make it difficult for human coders to encode the sample. The results show
309 that human coders can identify more nuanced, subtle, and complex frames than a computer model
310 would pick up on. Even so, human is better at processing the meaning of the text in tweets, where
311 the words are rather brief and used more creatively. Therefore, they can identify all frames,
312 regardless of their proportion. For example, the frame of Eastern countries' failure (in controlling
313 the crisis) was identified in only two tweets. This frame was later classified with others in the main
314 theme Comparison of Countries' Performance. Nevertheless, such frames tend to be eliminated by
315 the computer model because of their small percentage. We will discuss in the next section to what
316 extent the machine results are comparable to the human-driven codes.

317 ***LDA Outputs***

318 Below we present the results of the LDA topic model for each sample. Following Maier et al.
319 (2018), we summarize the LDA output for each sample in a table. In addition, we have added
320 additional columns to allow the analysis of the comparison of LDA topics with qualitative
321 networked frames based on the work of Nicholls & Culpepper (2020). The first three columns
322 contain some statistical information about each topic. The proportion and number of the documents
323 show the dominant topics in each sample in descending order. Each table has a column with a
324 label. As we explained in the Methods section, these labels were assigned to each topic after a
325 close examination of the top keywords and a qualitative interpretation of the top tweets. The next
326 column shows the top 10 words in each topic. The "degree of coherence" (DoC) column shows the
327 degree of homogeneity of tweets in a topic. If the tweets culminating in a topic denote the same
328 theme (represented by its label), the topic is more coherent. The last two columns show the degree
329 of compatibility (DoCom) of a topic with some networked frames and equated frames. In other
330 words, DoC indicates whether a topic is homogeneous enough to be described by a label. DoCom
331 indicates whether this label has an equivalent in qualitative frames. In this way, each table provides
332 a comprehensive understanding of the LDA result and its compatibility with the qualitative
333 examination.

334 **Table 1.**

335 Table 1 shows some interesting results on the performance of LDA in the RT network. Despite the
336 research team's attempts to assign meaningful and reliable labels to the topics after a thorough
337 qualitative analysis, some topics do not lend themselves to meaningful or reliable names. In fact,
338 they are too incongruent to be labeled (topics 2, 9, and 11). In some cases, LDA classified some
339 tweets with the same discursive practices, not frames. For instance, topic 2 is dedicated to users'
340 sarcasms and criticisms, mostly in the form of jokes and funny tweets. However, these messages
341 were aimed at different targets: the state, religious figures and beliefs, and people, including the
342 users themselves. As such, they contained various networked frames (sub-frames) such as FC (IRI,
343 people, religious figures), RDM (China's mendacity and secrecy, authorities abusing the situation,
344 emphasis on not using security forces), and the role of religion (absurdity). Nevertheless, while
345 LDA was able to identify that the underlying discursive practice of these tweets (sarcasm) was the

346 same, it was not able to identify that the targets of the sarcastic tweets varied. While this result
347 shows the weakness of LDA in detecting frames, it proves that LDA can be usefully employed to
348 detect the underlying discursive practices in textual data. Such groupings may not be of interest
349 from a frame analysis perspective, but they could help researchers study discursive practices in
350 large datasets more efficiently. Research on stylistic variation in texts could particularly benefit
351 from this strength of LDA. Nonetheless, there were more cases where the LDA topics did not even
352 share the same discursive practices, and the included tweets were largely scattered.

353 Further analysis showed that LDA usually provides us with more straightforward and clear themes.
354 Even coherent topics (at different levels) have some general labels. They can give us an initial
355 understanding of the content but not an exact mapping. Table 1 shows that LDA performs better
356 on lexical meanings than on compositional semantics². In other words, the performance of LDA
357 in classifying tweets containing simpler and one-dimensional information was more satisfactory.
358 Examples include topics 5 and 8, in which users shared health instructions (including Covid-19
359 properties). Such messages rarely contained hidden political and cultural meanings. As a result,
360 LDA successfully classified these topics within meaningful boundaries.

361 In contrast, topics with compositional meanings were less coherent and consistent with single and
362 exclusive frames. Topic 1 includes many tweets that discuss the government's inability to control
363 the crisis. Many tweets with political and social connotations could be found within this topic. In
364 general, two main groups fight over this subject: those defending the regime, and those questioning
365 it. However, the human coders were able to find more nuanced ways to discuss these issues. For
366 example, they were able to detect disagreement about the regime's performance on these issues.

367 Moreover, the different DoC levels show that in all topics, there were tweets that deviated from
368 the main theme. Such tweets could be found even in topics with a high coherence level. However,
369 the higher the DoC score, the greater the chance of finding a representative label and equivalent
370 networked framework for a topic. In the RT network, all topics with a DoC higher than "low" have
371 an analogous networked frame. Furthermore, while coherent topics could form some frames

² In short, lexical semantics refers to the meaning attributed to individual words in a text, as well as the disambiguation of such words through contextualization (Johnson, 2007). Compositional semantics refers to the way words are combined to create larger meanings (Pelletier, 1994).

372 besides the identified networked frames, in this case that was not the case. All coherent topics in
373 this sample corresponded to some networked frames and did not create any new frames.

374 On the contrary, there are several networked frames that were not found in the LDA topics. For
375 example, none of the themes related to proving previous arguments or economic and class issues.
376 This finding shows that using only LDA results to infer the underlying meaning in a text corpus
377 can mislead researchers and lead to incorrect interpretations of such results. Our analyses show
378 that qualitative interpretations are indispensable to understanding and identifying all embedded
379 meanings in textual content, e.g., tweets. Nevertheless, it is worth noting that LDA topics might
380 be associated with top frames. This means that LDA overlooked lesser featured networked frames.

381 Our qualitative interpretations also showed that most of the topics were highly interlinked, e.g.,
382 topics 2, 1, 3, and 4. Consistent with previous findings, this result indicates that LDA cannot
383 generate separate and comprehensive topics. Our analyses indicated that a predominant theme was
384 supported in one topic but was also present in lesser amounts in several other topics. This was
385 mainly due to the mixed membership approach. It also happens with human-driven coding, but our
386 analyses yielded a greater number of overlapping topics. For example, topics 0 and 7 or 5 and 8
387 are highly identical, and it makes sense to treat them as a single topic. LDA missed this. Moreover,
388 the most common qualitative frames are found in all LDA topics, e.g., FC and IP. This shows that
389 LDA is a good technique for finding the most dominant themes but at the expense of the less
390 prominent topics.

391 Samples 2 and 3: Tables 2 and 3 in Appendix 2 provide information on how LDA works for the
392 next samples. Since these tables are very large and contain more or less the same information as
393 Table 1, we have included them in a separate appendix.

394 The results show that the number of topics with lower DoC is higher in samples 2 and 3. This
395 shows that the performance of LDA does not improve when the number of documents is reduced.
396 Surprisingly, LDA performs worse in such cases. This result also shows that we can easily apply
397 LDA to the RT network or to the entire datasets in other studies and obtain the same or even better
398 results.

399 The analysis of samples 2 and 3 also confirms most of the results of the analysis of the RT network
400 (sample 1). For example, LDA also works better for lexical meanings in these samples or in the
401 case of overlapping topics. In particular, the results show that LDA is a suitable technique for
402 finding the most dominant themes in the text. Moreover, the discursive and qualitative analyses of
403 all samples confirm that the top keywords cannot provide even a half-acceptable understanding of
404 the content of the tweets. There is a significant gap between the top words and the actual tweets
405 on each topic. One reason for this could be the fact that there are some tweets in each topic with a
406 high contribution percentage (CP)³, which probably influence the process of selecting the top
407 keywords. For example, topic 5 in Sample 3, a topic with a very low DoC, has one tweet with a
408 CP of 24. Then the CP drops significantly to 15. The first tweet contains words like "apparatus,
409 IRGC, test, and produce." Most tweets on this topic lack these words, but they are among the top
410 keywords. For example, the 6th tweet on this topic, with a CP of 14, does not contain any of the
411 top keywords.

412 The gap between the top keywords and the grounded themes highlights the importance of
413 qualitative interpretation of LDA topics. In particular, we cannot infer the meaning of a topic by
414 looking at the top word in the Persian text. Therefore, human examination of the tweets per LDA
415 topic is an indispensable phase in evaluating the LDA results. In the last section, we will discuss
416 these and other results to show how this research advances our understanding of computational
417 methods vis-a-vis qualitative interpretations.

418 **Discussion**

419 While computational techniques have been used extensively in the social sciences to challenge,
420 supplement, or extend long-standing theories, their application in frame analysis is still uncertain
421 (van Atteveldt & Peng, 2018). Nonetheless, most research in this area has focused on the
422 automated detection of different types of frames, e.g., generic and context-specific frames in news
423 articles (Burscher et al., 2014; Walter & Ophir, 2019). As a result, researchers have relatively
424 failed to investigate the capabilities of topic models in automatically detecting networked frames,
425 which are another form of framing in social media. Other relevant questions also remain

³ The CP shows the influence of a tweet on the composition of a topic. A higher value of CP means that the tweet plays a more important role in the formation of a topic by LDA.

426 unanswered, such as to what extent does a single LDA topic correspond to a networked frame?
427 What impact does the imported dataset have on the reliability of LDA results? Since previous
428 research has mainly focused on English and other common languages, the ability of topic models
429 to interpret other languages remains unknown. We focus on Persian Twitter to fill this gap as
430 another contribution of this study. We have attempted to advance the existing literature by
431 combining a comparative approach based on LDA topic models and human-driven qualitative
432 coding.

433 First, this research provides more insight into the extent to which a topic can be considered a frame.
434 While LDA categorizes tweets into loose categories, it cannot produce pure frames with clear
435 boundaries. Frames are something more than LDA raw topics. Indeed, our results support previous
436 studies that challenged the idea of equating LDA topics with frames (Walter & Ophir, 2019).
437 Consistent with previous studies (Nicholls & Culpepper, 2020), we have shown that there is always
438 a gap between LDA topics and grounded frames. There is no reliable statistical method for
439 measuring this distance to date. We emphasize that human interpretation is crucial in deciding how
440 far LDA outputs are from networked frames.

441 In our three cases, only four of the topics have DoC scores of the highest level. Therefore, they are
442 able to more easily find their correspondence in networked frames. Regardless of the low number
443 of these topics, there are even tweets that deviate from the predominant themes in such highly
444 coherent cases. It is more difficult to equate topics with lower DoC with networked frames. In such
445 cases, manual review of tweets and investigation of topics are essential. The high number of topics
446 with very low, low, and medium DoC confirms that LDA is not a powerful method to identify
447 networked frames at a satisfactory level.

448 Our analyses also indicated that some topics should be merged to form a frame. In contrast, other
449 topics span multiple frames. For topics with very low and low DoC, the number of frames in a
450 topic is so high that no label can even describe it. It also shows that LDA topics usually overlap.
451 The same frames can be found in many topics, which significantly reduces the performance of
452 LDA in frame detection.

453 Nevertheless, the fact of overlapping frames provides an advantage in automated frame detection.
454 The results show that LDA can identify the most important topics in large text data. This study's

455 qualitative analysis showed that FC, RDM, and IP are the most networked frames on Persian
456 Twitter. LDA topics could be largely equated with them. Thus, while LDA does not detect less
457 dominant frames, it can be used to quickly identify the most prominent frames. The results also
458 reflect previous studies arguing that the topic model works better with lexical meanings than with
459 compositional semantics (Rodriguez & Storer, 2020). Overall, we argue that LDA is a satisfactory
460 method for analyzing the lexical web of meanings and identifying top frames. As a result, we
461 question the idea of equating topics with frames, as has been claimed in some research (DiMaggio
462 et al., 2013; Gilardi et al., 2021). However, we have demonstrated that this method effectively
463 extracts the most important themes in large text data. If researchers want to go further and better
464 understand their data, human coding is required.

465 Human interpretation is important for other purposes as well. We have shown that there is a
466 discrepancy between the top keywords in each topic and the grounded themes. A qualitative review
467 is the most reliable way to measure this gap. In line with Maier et al. (2018), we believe that
468 eliminating human-driven analysis seriously challenges the validity of LDA results. This means
469 that the trade-off between streetlight syndrome and fully automated systems is inevitable. A
470 researcher should decide to what extent to rely on fully automated systems depending on research
471 goals, time, and other resources.

472 This research also confirms the existing literature that argues that computational methods work
473 better with clearly delineated and general concepts (De Grove et al., 2020; Grimmer & Stewart,
474 2013). LDA provided such topics in all cases. This is also consistent with our findings mentioned
475 above. Moreover, our study showed that the larger the sample size, the more reliable LDA
476 produces results in the RT network. While we expected LDA to perform more efficiently on
477 smaller datasets, its performance was worse on smaller and more coherent samples. Nicholls &
478 Culpepper (2020) also argued that topic model outputs are not highly acceptable even with more
479 targeted datasets. While they used datasets from different sources, we imported samples of the
480 same dataset to evaluate the automated results. However, the results showed that LDA performed
481 better on a larger, logically less-targeted dataset.

482 While our focus was on comparing LDA outputs with qualitative interpretations, which is a gap in
483 the existing literature, this study also extended our knowledge of applying computational methods

484 to less dominant languages. LDA shows slight weakness for Persian compared to other prominent
485 languages such as English (Burscher et al., 2014; Nicholls & Culpepper, 2020; Rodriguez &
486 Storer, 2020; Walter & Ophir, 2019). Compared to other languages, Persian has fewer
487 computational tools and resources. For example, while Rodriguez & Storer (2020) used LIWC⁴
488 software for semantic evaluation of their results, we cannot do the same for Persian. Moreover, to
489 our knowledge, there is no dictionary for tokenization or lemmatization in Persian. That could
490 impair the efficiency of computational techniques in Persian. Therefore, we believe that more tools
491 should be developed for lesser-known languages to enable researchers in such areas to contribute
492 more effectively to ongoing research. In this study, we omitted lemmatization and tokenization, as
493 they are too resource intensive and previous studies have not found them to affect the performance
494 of the model. However, creating and using a tool to do these things can deepen our understanding.

495 In line with Nicholls and Culpepper (2020), who argue for more research to understand the
496 efficiency of LDA in analyzing different input data, we sought to provide more empirical evidence
497 by studying networked frames on Twitter in a little-studied domain and on three different samples.
498 As mentioned earlier, this research shows that the performance of LDA in detecting networked
499 frames is similarly efficient as in extracting other types of frames in news articles (Burggraaff &
500 Trilling, 2020; Burscher et al., 2014; Walter & Ophir, 2019). This finding proves that the weakness
501 of LDA in understanding human meaning is something fundamental. It is not likely to depend on
502 the type of frame studied, notwithstanding some minor differences in results. The results in three
503 different samples underscore this. The results of performing LDA on all samples were not
504 completely acceptable. Moreover, we have shown that while LDA performs slightly better on
505 English and other major languages, its performance on Persian texts is weak. Further research is
506 needed to demonstrate how LDA can be improved to produce more coherent and reliable topics
507 across different languages and datasets.

508 We also acknowledge that various decisions, such as the choice of K, may affect the results.
509 However, this limitation is inevitable as current topic modeling approaches have not satisfactorily
510 addressed this issue (Maier et al., 2018). In addition, we used Gensim to perform LDA. Using

⁴ Linguistic Inquiry and Word Count (LIWC) is a word counting software program that refers to a dictionary of grammatical, psychological, and content word categories.

511 other tools, such as the *lda* package in R, could lead to different results. However, we believe that
512 using such methods would likely not significantly affect the results of this study.

513 Despite these caveats, our study provides LDA as an acceptable technique for detecting the most
514 important frames, especially those containing lexical meaning, even in larger datasets in Persian.
515 Of course, the results showed that the performance of the LDA model does not satisfy all the
516 requirements necessary to be considered satisfactory. The results also showed the importance of
517 human interpretation in several steps of automated frame extraction. LDA is reliable in deriving
518 the main grounded themes when researchers want a quick and less accurate analysis. Systematic
519 and intensive qualitative coding (of text) and interpretation (of LDA outputs) are essential to
520 identify more detailed and nuanced grounded frames. While the study mainly concerns
521 monolingual topic modeling, it could be employed in developing approaches in multilingual
522 topic modeling. Lind et al., (2021) discussed the various approaches to multilingual topic
523 modeling. They proposed the “Polylingual Topic Model” (PLTM) as a valid approach in this field.
524 The result of this investigation could be used in line with this approach to enhance multilingual
525 topic modeling including big Persian text. In this way, this study sets more directions for further
526 investigation, particularly in understudied languages.

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